

Integrated germplasm improvement

Yield potential of irrigated IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V at Ndop Plain

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Rice, a relatively new crop in Cameroon, is grown on about 20,000 ha of irrigated land. Ndop Plain, one of three major rice production areas, is situated at 1,200 m above sea level. Irrigated rice is grown on an estimated 3,000 ha; a further 15,000 ha is potentially suitable for rice cultivation. The major constraints to increased rice production are low temperatures during the growing season and associated problems of diseases such as sheath rot (ShR) and grain discoloration (Gd).

Tainan V is still being grown by some farmers because of its good taste. But its poor grain quality (bold, short, chalky grain, and poor keeping quality) does not compete with imported rice in the open market. In 1987, IR7167-33-2-3 was released for general cultivation. It has superior grain quality (medium-long, less chalky, and fair keeping quality), yield, cold tolerance, and resistance to ShR and Gd.

We collected data over several seasons of experiment station and farmers' field trials to compare yields. In experiment station yield trials, early transplanting, 25- × 20-cm spacing, and rate of 2-3 seedlings/hill were practiced. Fertilizers were applied at 60-17.6-33 kg NPK/ha. In farmers' field trials, nursery, transplanting, and crop management were according to normal practices and calendar.

Table 1 shows results of 1987 and 1988 yield trials at Bamunka research site. In 1987, Tainan V yields ranged from 3.2 to 5.0 t/ha; IR7167-33-2-3 yields ranged from 4.9 to 6.3 t/ha. The highest yielding plot of Tainan V achieved 80% of the yield of IR7167-33-2-3 in the same trial and 91% of the mean of IR7167-33-2-3. In 1988 experiment station trials, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V by an average 36%. Tainan V yielded 2.7-3.7 t/ha, IR7167-33-2-3 4.3-5.5 t/ha.

IR7167-33-2-3 also showed greater resistance to ShR and Gd.

Table 2 shows results from farmers' field trials in the Bamunka farm area. In 1987, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V on all six farms sampled, by margins of 28-65%. Yields of Tainan V ranged from 2.7 to 5.4 t/ha, IR7167-33-2-3 from 3.4 to 6.3 t/ha. Yields in 1988 were similar.

IR7167-33-2-3 has an average yield advantage over Tainan V of about 32% at Bamunka farm and 45% in farmers' fields. Its performance was consistent over 2 yr. □

Table 2. Yields of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in farmers' fields at Ndop Plain, Cameroon, 1987-88.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
	1987	1988
Tainan V	3.4	3.2
IR7167-33-2-3	4.9	4.5

^aMean of 6 farms sampled each year.

Table 1. Performance of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in experiment station yield trials. Ndop Plain, Bamunka, Cameroon, 1987-88.

Variety or line	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Duration (d)	Reaction ^b to		Panicle exsertion ^b (0-9)
	1987	1988		Sheath rot (0-9)	Grain discoloration (0-9)	
IR7167-33-2-3	5.5	4.4	142	3	3	3

^aMean of 6 trials each year. ^bStandard evaluation system for rice.

ITA173, a high-yielding rice variety for irrigated areas in Tanzania

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We tested a number of entries from IRTP nurseries at DRC under irrigated condition in the 1983 wet season. ITA173 was identified as promising and was tested in observation and preliminary yield trials in 1983 and

Yield performance of ITA173 in trials at 4 locations in Tanzania, 1985-87 dry and wet seasons.

Year and season	Location and region	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		ITA173	Local check
1985 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	4.7	2.5 (Katrin)
1985 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	7.7	4.3 (IR579)
1985 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	7.6	4.9 (Katrin)
1985 Dry	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	4.4	3.3 (Katrin)
1986 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	7.1	4.5 (Supa)
1986 Wet	DRF Farms-Morogoro	4.3	3.9 (IR8)
1986 Wet	Igurusi-Mbeya	6.1	3.8 (Kihogo)
1986 Wet	Mwamapuli Igunga-Tabora	4.4	2.4 (Supa)
1986 Dry	DRF Farms-Morogoro	7.0	5.6 (Katrin)
1987 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	6.8	3.6 (Supa)
1987 Dry	Dry Farms-Morogoro	7.8	5.6 (Katrin)
Mean		6.2	

1984 dry and wet seasons. It also was evaluated with other selected varieties and breeding lines in station, zonal, and national variety trials at four locations 1985-87.

Mean yield was 6.2 t/ha (range 4.3-7.8 t/ha) across the trials and locations (see table). ITA173

outyielded check varieties by 10-88% and ranked first or second in 11 trials.

ITA173 is intermediate in height (105 cm) and has good field resistance to common diseases and insects (*Diopsis* spp.). It matures 2-3 wk earlier (115 d) than Supa and IR8, the varieties most widely grown by small

farm holders and commercial rice farms, respectively. ITA173 also has better cooking and eating quality than IR8. It is recommended to both small farm holders and state-owned commercial rice farms. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Relationship between urease activity and some rice soil properties

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Urease activity in soil is an important factor in N fertilizer management for

rice. The speed of hydrolysis and the release of N from urea into soil depends largely on urease activity. Once the N contained in urea is released, it is subjected to physical, chemical, and biological processes that ultimately determine how much N in applied urea will be available to the rice crop.

Determination of urease activity is costly and time-consuming. However,

urease activity is known to be closely related to some soil properties that could give an indirect measure. We studied the relationships between urease activity and some properties of rice soils.

Soil samples (0-20 cm depth) collected from ricefields in different areas of Bangladesh were dried, crushed, and passed through a 2-mm sieve. The soils varied in total N, organic matter, clay content, pH, and CEC (Table 1).

Each soil was analyzed for urease activity. Urease activity varied from 2.70 to 8.06 μg urea hydrolyzed/g soil per h (Table 1). It correlated significantly with total N ($r = 0.63^*$) and clay content ($r = 0.70^*$).

No significant correlation between urease activity and any other soil property was found (Table 2). □

Table 1. Some properties of soils collected from ricefields in 10 locations in Bangladesh and their urease activities.

Location	USPA and taxonomy	Total N (%)	Organic matter (%)	pH	Clay (%)	CEC (meq/100 g)	Urease activity ^a
Thakurgaon	Ustochrepts	0.07	1.25	5.1	15	10	4.75
Bogra	Haplaquepts	0.14	2.29	5.5	37	9	7.81
Ishurdi	Haplaquepts	0.13	1.94	7.5	37	26	8.04
Rajshahi	Albaquepts	0.08	1.04	7.6	23	15	6.45
Satkhira	Haplaquepts	0.15	3.02	7.5	23	37	4.44
Faridpur	Haplaquepts	0.13	1.77	7.3	39	17	8.04
Sonagazi	Fluvaquepts	0.04	1.01	7.3	24	10	2.70
Joydebpur	Paleudults	0.13	2.05	6.2	33	18	8.06
Patuakhali	Haplaquepts	0.12	2.08	5.5	37	19	5.73
Gazipur	Paleudults	0.10	1.87	4.9	28	13	5.04
Range		0.043-0.15	1.01-2.29	4.9-7.6	15.10-38.90	9.2-37.0	2.70-8.06

^a μg hydrolyzed/g soil per h.

Table 2. Correlations and estimated relationships of urease activity (UA) in 10 rice soils with some of soil properties. Bangladesh.

Soil property	Linear equation	r^a
N	UA = 2.33 + 34.2 N	0.63*
Organic matter (OM)	UA = 4.91 + 0.69 OM	0.29 ^{ns}
Clay	UA = 1.24 + 0.16 clay	0.70*
pH	UA = 5.43 + 0.10 pH	0.06 ^{ns}
CEC	UA = 5.82 + 0.02 CEC	0.07 ^{ns}

^a* = significant at the 5% level.

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